

George Castrioti Scanderbeg (1405-1468)

Written in January 2018 by Agron Elezi

Mankind has seldom known truly invincible warriors, figures whose stories are as awe-inspiring as they are bloodstained; whose sheer force of character transcends nearly every archetype of heroes. While the heroes portrayed in historical literature and Hollywood films are often glorified, these warriors - who shone with their brilliance in the darkest chapters of history - were real. And there have been only a few of them.

Once upon a time, there was such a warrior, who, with a standing army of about 2,500 cavalymen, fought successfully on two fronts, against both East and West, confronting the two superpowers of his era. What follows, drawn from the spirit of my cultural heritage and my personal perspective, is the story of an unbreakable swordsman, a marvel of military tactics who left a profound mark on European history. His heroic feats, as noted by Major General James Wolfe (1727–1759), commander of the British army, "are immeasurable; for he excels all the officers, ancient and modern."

I will present, as concisely as possible, his journey, his character, and his true stature "matchable to the greatest of the great" as portrayed by the Elizabethan poet Edmund Spenser (1552–1599).

With deepest respect and highest appreciation, this essay is dedicated to my national hero, Gjergj Kastrioti Skënderbeu (George Castrioti Scanderbeg), on the 550th anniversary of his death.

War on Two Fronts – Legendary Fighters

In 1447, war broke out between Skanderbeg, commander of the Albanian League, and the Republic of Venice, one of the leading economic and trading powers of medieval Europe. At that time, Albania - reduced to a small collection of fortresses and mountain cantons - consisted of a few independent principalities. A portion of Albania's western region was already under Venetian control, while from the east loomed the constant threat of the Ottoman Empire, a rising superpower emerging from the ruins of the Byzantine world.

On July 23, 1448, a Venetian army of 14,000 troops mostly cavalry, was decisively defeated by Albanian knights at the Battle of the Drin. The surviving Venetians retreated to the castle of Dagnum, where they quickly appealed to the Ottomans for help. Skanderbeg left a contingent behind to maintain the siege and immediately turned eastward to confront the incoming Ottoman force.

Mustafa Pasha, leading a 15,000-strong Ottoman army, arrived shortly thereafter, but on August 14, 1448, his forces were crushed by Skanderbeg's mere 6,000 men at the Battle of Oranik. These two victories, won almost simultaneously on two fronts, are documented even in Venetian archival sources.

The news of these astonishing victories spread rapidly across Europe, greeted with great enthusiasm by prominent leaders of the late medieval world. To many, it seemed like a miracle: two mighty armies, one representing the power of the West, the other of the East, defeated by a single small force within weeks.

The League of Albanian Princes, founded and led by Skanderbeg, never exceeded 10,000 troops. His standing army, consisting of just 2,500 elite cavalymen, functioned as his personal guard—described by chroniclers as a “praetorian cohort.” This small but unbreakable force was the cornerstone of Skanderbeg’s countless victories, including his legendary resistance against grand Ottoman campaigns personally led by Sultan Murad II in 1450, and by Mehmed the Conqueror in 1466 and 1467.

The Ottoman historian Ibn Kemal (1468–1536) once remarked:

The Albanians, these tigers of mountain wars, have rebellion as their religion. Even their weakest warrior is among the bravest and strongest on the battlefield—as if he were a knight riding a horse of legend.

These elite warriors, including the Albanian princes whose names Skanderbeg knew by heart, deserve to be remembered and honored. Fortunately, some medieval sources still preserve their names and deeds. There are even accounts of a moving love story that emerged amid

the chaos of war—material ripe for a historical drama, a novel, or a screenplay.

With great respect, here are some of their names: Gjin Muzaka, Gjon Perlati, Gjin Maneshi, Dhimitër Berisha, Nikollë Berisha, Pjetër Emanueli, Zakaria Gropa, Vladan Gjurica, Mojs Gjurica, Muzaka i Angjelinës, Gjergj Kuka, Lek Kuka, Pal Dukagjini, Nikollë Dukagjini, Lek Zakaria Altisferi, Pjetër Spani, Lek Dushmani, Gjergj Stresi Balsha, Gjon Stresi Balsha, Andrea Topia, Tanush Topia, Gjergj Arianiti, Moisi of Dibra, Teodor Korona Muzaka, Hajdin Muzaka, Count Vrana Altisferi, and Hamza Kastrioti.

Skanderbeg was both an indomitable warrior and a brilliant strategist. Tall and athletic, with inexhaustible energy and resilience to both heat and cold, he was often found at the heart of the battle. Wielding a curved sword—or sometimes a mace—he fought with a blend of raw strength, lightning speed, and surgical precision. His most effective military asset as a general, however, was his rapid light cavalry, which struck with breathtaking speed and maneuverability.

Italian historian Antonio Coccio Sabellico (1436–1506) observed: *“Those who saw him at the head of his elite cavalry battalion could never forget that magnificent sight.”*

Sabellico’s father, who met Skanderbeg during his Italian campaign in 1461, often boasted that he had been lucky enough to behold this radiant, seemingly immortal warrior—*“a man worth an entire battalion on his own.”*

Thanks to his strategic genius and military prowess, Skanderbeg earned high praise from many scholars, including the Tyrolean historian Jakob Philipp Fallmerayer (1790–1861), who wrote: *“George Castrioti, as everyone knows, stands among the most accomplished, most successful, and greatest masters of the art of war in all time.”*

Scanderbeg’s Story – The War with the Ottoman Empire

In the spring of 1405, on the rocky ground of the Albanian highlands, between the clash of rising civilizations and among the last surviving tribes of a glorious ancient race, Gjergj Kastrioti was born. His father, Gjon, was an Albanian chieftain who ruled the north-central region of Albania known as Emathia and controlled the important trade route linking the Adriatic coast with the town of Prizren. As described by U.S. Congressman Joseph J. DioGuardi in his 2008 speech on Scanderbeg, Gjon “had kept the invading Ottoman Turks at bay for more than twenty years when he was forced into a deceptive peace treaty in 1422 with Sultan Murad II to secure the rear of the Turkish army in Southeast Europe and spare the lives of his people from the wrath of the Ottoman Empire. To guarantee the arrangement, the Sultan took Gjon's youngest son, Gjergj, hostage to Adrianople, the European capital of the Ottoman Empire.”

Converted to Islam, the hostages of noble families were often sent to the empire's best military academies and trained to become future Janissaries and commanders. Immersed in this elite environment, Gjergj quickly made an amazing career thanks to the "golden proportion" of his body, mind, and courage. Educated at the Enderun School, he was soon appointed commander of a cavalry unit and led several victorious campaigns for the Sultan in Asia. During his time in the Ottoman court, he also gained fame for his prowess in duels, reportedly defeating a formidable Tartar warrior reputed to be invincible.

Sultan Murad II was greatly impressed by Gjergj, and, as legend holds, treated him almost as his own son. The Sultan honored him with the name and title "Iskender Bey" (Scanderbeg), meaning Lord Alexander, in tribute to Alexander the Great - a name Gjergj would bear for life.

As his stature grew, so too did a persistent inner call. It was the call of his homeland, his people, and the legacy of his ancestors - a longing for freedom, dignity, and sovereignty. That opportunity came in 1443, as Fan Noli describes, when Kasim Beg was defeated by Hunyadi near Nish. Scanderbeg defected from the Ottoman army and rushed to Albania. With forged documents, he seized the castle of Kruja and, on November 28, 1443, raised the red banner with the black double-headed eagle.

Supported immediately by his compatriots, who were always ready to resist foreign feudal lords, Scanderbeg

rapidly reclaimed his paternal territories, liberating a chain of fortresses from Kruja to Sfetigrad that had been under Ottoman control.

By the end of that first winter, realizing he could not resist the Sultan alone, Scanderbeg convened a gathering of Albanian chieftains. On March 2, 1444, in the Cathedral of Saint Nicholas in Lezha, the League of Albanian Princes was formed, and Scanderbeg was unanimously elected commander-in-chief, as confirmed by Noli's archival research.

However, the emergence of a strong Albanian League worried the Venetians, who feared losing their holdings in Albania. They worked actively to undermine and, if possible, dissolve the League. Thus, Scanderbeg's revolt against the Ottomans was complicated by sporadic conflicts with Venice and its political intrigues.

In June 1444, Sultan Murad dispatched his most seasoned general, Ali Pasha, at the head of 25,000 troops to punish Scanderbeg. But Ali Pasha was ambushed in the narrow valley of Torviolli, in lower Dibra, by the newly united Albanian League, and was soundly defeated. As Marin Barleti wrote: "Lions on that day were led by lions", a tribute to Scanderbeg's generals and the fierce valor of his warriors. This victory was hailed by Pope Eugene IV, the Kingdom of Hungary, and Philippe le Bon, Duke of Burgundy.

On April 21, 1451, joy spread across Albania. Bells rang in castles and countryside alike as Scanderbeg married Donika, daughter of Gjergj Arianit Komneni, chieftain of Kanina and Shpata. Their union produced one son, Gjon Kastrioti II.

From the moment he raised his flag, Scanderbeg faced nearly continuous attacks from the Ottoman army. Except for two brief pauses, each year brought one or more campaigns against him. Yet, as Gjin Muzaka recorded, "Then began the continuous wars of the Turks in Albania, in which many chieftains and gentlemen died... and the forces of the Turks were always increasing while ours were decreasing... almost all the young men of Albania were killed... there were only a few old men left... and our cantons were dwindling... still we were defending ourselves as best we could."

Over twenty-four major battles were fought, and many more skirmishes. Despite dwindling resources, Scanderbeg never wavered, even in the direst situations. His resistance was immortalized in the sieges of Kruja in 1450, 1466, and 1467, in which he stood against the might of two of the greatest Sultans of the Ottoman Empire and armies numbering over 100,000.

The 1467 campaign was particularly devastating. Mehmed II, with a huge 250,000 of his troops, attacked and harassed the entire country; and while the castle of Kruja was resisting heroically for the third time, he burned everything that could be burned, destroyed all the

countryside, and killed all Albanian civilians who couldn't escape or hide. His rage was out of control, and derived from two reasons: He wanted to break once and for all the Scanderbeg's resistance who is hindering him toward his direction and his dream - reaching and conquering the West capital of the ancient Roman Empire - Rome; and, as a revenge of two prior unsuccessful expeditions held personally by him and his father, revenge to the big shame of his powerful empire stopped by such a small country like Albania. His message was more than clear - to flatten everything Albanian that had so far dared to oppose the Ottoman Empire, and kill them all.

Scanderbeg and his picked bravest fighters, as he had done in the previous situations, were acting from the outside of the castle with his blitz raids - hit and run tactics; and as legend says was settled in the caves of highest mountains. After the Sultan's vain attempt to capture the fortress of Kruja, before the autumn of the same year, still in anger, he left Albania as a black dreadful image full of ashes, still smoking, and with shocking wails - a landscape in Hell.

After this apocalypse, Scanderbeg tirelessly appealed to Western powers for aid and labored to restore the shattered morale of his people. But in the harsh winter of 1468, weakened by exposure and exhaustion, he fell ill and died of fever on January 17.

"Choirs of Albanian maidens," writes Sabellicus, "though surrounded by the din of battle and the clang of barbarian

arms, assembled regularly every eighth day in the public squares to sing hymns to their departed hero.”

Scanderbeg’s spirit endured among his people. Resistance held until 1478, when Kruja finally fell, and in 1479, the last bastion, Shkodra, was surrendered. A decade after his death, the Ottomans overran his lands. So feared and revered was he that Turkish soldiers opened his grave and took fragments of his bones, believing they would gain invincibility from the remains of the man once known as Iskender Bey.

Scanderbeg’s Allies – The Italian Expedition

The Roman Catholic world, as Fan Noli notes, which at the time encompassed nearly all of Europe - excluding Russia and the Balkan Peninsula - was deeply invested in Scanderbeg’s struggle against the Ottoman Turks. The countries bordering the Adriatic Sea - such as the Papal States, the Kingdom of Naples, the Republic of Ragusa, and the Kingdom of Hungary - felt especially threatened by the looming Turkish advance and did their best to assist the Albanians in halting the invaders at their doorstep. Though their support was often limited and insufficient, it was nonetheless significant enough to elevate the Albanian resistance to epic proportions.

Several Popes came to Scanderbeg's aid, recognizing him as the "*Champion of Christendom.*" Pope Nicholas V (1447–1453), Calixtus III (1453–1458), Pius II (1458–1464), and Paul II (1464–1473) contributed thousands of golden ducats from the papal treasury to support his cause.

Alphonse V of Aragon (1396–1458), King of Naples, proved to be Scanderbeg's most loyal ally. Their relationship deepened after 1448, when both fought Venice on opposing sides of the Adriatic. Alphonse - also King of Aragon - had ambitions of building a Mediterranean Catalan Empire stretching from Barcelona to Constantinople. In pursuit of this dream, he frequently supplied Scanderbeg with ammunition, food, auxiliary troops, and funds. One of his commanders, Count Vrana Altisferi, later became a trusted companion of Scanderbeg and the famed defender of the fortress of Kruja.

Three years after Alphonse's death, in 1460, his son King Ferdinand faced a major rebellion by Neapolitan barons and a threat from the French pretender, René d'Anjou. In September of that year, Scanderbeg sent a contingent of 500 cavalry under the command of his nephew, John Stresi Balsha, to assist Ferdinand.

Ferdinand's main rival, Giovanni Antonio Orsini, attempted to dissuade Scanderbeg from intervening. He sent a letter proposing an alternative alliance and, with aristocratic condescension, remarked that the Albanian expedition would be worthless against his superior cavalry. Scanderbeg's reply, dated October 10, 1460, stands

as a testament to his character. In it, he wrote that he was not a *condottiere* - a mercenary seeking profit - but a man of virtue who stood by his allies. He reminded Orsini that Albanians (Epirotes) never betrayed their friends and that he owed loyalty to the Aragonese, especially in times of hardship.

In a striking appeal to classical heritage, Scanderbeg wrote:

“We call ourselves Epirotes. And you must know that our predecessors came to your country (Southern Italy) many times... and fought the Romans in great battles. We believe they brought more glory than shame.”

This correspondence became a historical treasure, revealing Scanderbeg's loyalty, gratitude, and knightly honor. It also reflected his knowledge of classical history and his deep pride in his ancestry. By invoking the legacy of Pyrrhus and antiquity, Scanderbeg's name grew even more renowned during the European Renaissance.

To free himself to assist his Western ally, Scanderbeg needed to secure peace in the East. He proposed a one-year truce with the Ottoman Empire. Given Scanderbeg's former high standing in the Ottoman court, and the fact that he had proven to be unlike other Balkan leaders who quickly capitulated, Sultan Mehmed II agreed to the truce on April 27, 1461, secretly hoping that Scanderbeg might eventually be persuaded to return to Ottoman service.

With the Eastern front temporarily quiet, Scanderbeg prepared for the Italian campaign. On August 25, 1461, he arrived in Barletta, Calabria, with the remainder of his troops, cavalymen and archers. At that time, King Ferdinand was trapped in a besieged castle. Scanderbeg acted swiftly. Using agile light cavalry tactics, he overwhelmed the sluggish Italian heavy cavalry, causing panic and disarray.

Giovanni Pontano (1426–1503), an eyewitness and King Ferdinand’s chancellor, recorded: “His name and his arrival not only confounded the enemies and their plans but filled all Italy with his fame and reputation.”

After a series of engagements, Scanderbeg defeated the forces of Orsini and the Angevins, secured Ferdinand’s throne, and returned to Albania in January 1462.

Driving Force

In the 15th century, the Albanians were predominantly Christian, though not fervently religious. Scanderbeg himself was a typical reflection of his people, guided more by his ancestral code of honor than dogma. For the sake of his people, and their unwavering loyalty in all aspects of life, he reconverted to Christianity. Yet, he never renounced the Muslim name *Iskender Bey* (Alexander the Great), which he bore with pride. That name, laden with historical resonance, evoked the grandeur of antiquity, not

religious affiliation. In all his letters and official documents, he signed himself with the name *Scanderbeg*, and at times proudly proclaimed himself a descendant of Pyrrhus of Epirus, heir to Alexander the Great, and spiritual successor to the heroes of Homer's *Iliad*, including Achilles.

He often adorned his helmet and insignia with classical symbols, testaments to his cultivated identity, tied not to a religious cause or to the political struggles of the major world powers, but to a deeper, ancestral calling. His defection from the Ottoman Empire was not a political maneuver or a religious act; it was a spiritual awakening, an assertion of a soul that refused submission. It was an act born of tradition, of dignity, of the unbroken expectation of freedom that his people carried through the centuries.

Viewed through the lens of art and spirit, his uprising could be likened to a Renaissance revelation, charged with the romantic nobility of Wagnerian overtures; an opening to a sublime and tragic national drama.

Undeniably, the driving force that animated Scanderbeg throughout his life was the profound influence of his origins, his bloodline, his culture, and his mythic consciousness. Together with his knights, he stood on a foundation built not only of strategy and steel, but of ancestral memory. They were sustained by warrior legends breathed through epic songs and battle-rhythmic dances; by the ideal of *mens sana in corpore sano*; the balanced mind within a perfected body; by a fierce longing for divine beauty, as envisioned in *E bukura e dheut* ("The Earthly

Beauty”); and by sacred Albanian values such as Family and Besa (sacred oath). Their “religion,” if one can call it that, stood above the Ten Commandments, above canon law and Shariat alike. It was the wisdom of the mountains - their own Code (*Kanun*) - that governed their lives.

With regard to codes of conduct, many of the peoples described as “barbarians” in the Middle Ages, such as the Slavs who settled in the Balkans, the Russians, and the early Germans—lacked elaborated codes of honor prior to their adoption of a major religion. Their moral frameworks were imported from faith: the Slavs and Russians through Orthodox Christianity, the Germans through Catholic Christianity, and the Turko-Mongol peoples through Islam. Religion thus became the primary source of their moral and juridical norms.

The French and English, and to some extent certain Germanic groups, did possess rudimentary codes of honor prior to the acceptance of Christianity, but these were restricted to the domains of knighthood, aristocracy, or a warrior elite. By contrast, the Albanians required no religious framework to define the principles of honor, besa (the pledged word of trust), hospitality, or blood (kinship and vengeance). These values were deeply embedded within their ancient customary code, long before the appearance of either biblical or Qur’anic writings.

This code endured even after the arrival of Abraham religions: Albanians preserved the Kanun despite converting to Orthodoxy, Catholicism, or Islam,

maintaining it until the emergence of the modern state. Furthermore, whereas among the aforementioned peoples the code of honor generally applied only to the social or military elite, among Albanians it extended universally – from peasant to chieftain alike. It is thus unsurprising that the renowned Ottoman historian Ibn Kemal remarked of the Albanians “that even the weakest among them is one of the strongest and bravest,” since he, like all others, had been raised under the code.

A poignant illustration of this moral code as the supreme spiritual compass can be found in the Albanian rhapsody of *Gjergj Elez Alia*. His name is itself a fusion of Christianity (*Gjergj*) and Islam (*Ali*), but his soul is moved not by scripture, but by code. In difficult times for him – exhausted to the brink of death, under the pain of nine wounds received in numerous battles – his sister’s honor is threatened by a terrible foreign enemy. He rises from his bed, confronts the enemy, and says:

“You demanded my sister before the duel
Demanded herds from the Herdsman
But I have come here to show you,
That our ancestors left us a Code (*Kanun*)”

Here lies the true driving force, not religion, not wealth, but a sacred fidelity to ancestral law, the unwritten spiritual and moral order of a people who would rather die than break faith with their origin.

Epilogue – A Summary

Under normal circumstances, and even with favorable geography like Albania's, a small army could hardly stand against a superpower. Moreover, if that superpower is at times helped by another power from the opposite side, then how long could the small army survive on two fronts?

Scanderbeg stood firm for no less than a quarter of a century - 25 years. In that rich catalog of battles, we must also consider his early years, full of incredible duel victories and successful invasive campaigns in Asia while serving in the army of the Ottoman Empire, an inseparable part of the formation of his powerful martial identity.

Scanderbeg's character is revealed through his famous correspondence with the Italians, which proves he possessed a prominent noble soul, one that emerged from the powerful code of his predecessors. He was always ready to answer a friend's call for help under any circumstance and could afford additional battles with the Italians, marked as his glorious, triumphal expedition in Italy. His unbelievable journey, deeds, and endurance went beyond any story or myth. Consequently, his character surpasses any archetype.

Thousands of books have been written about Scanderbeg all over the world - poems, novels, historical accounts, articles, essays, and more. Through the generations of his descendants, many fragments of his battles have been preserved and transmitted through epic songs. All of this

literature - including legends, no matter how magnificent they may sound - can be justified by historical archival sources.

Otherwise, any attempt by a historian to depreciate, condemn, confuse, or divert his character and origin using suspicious and indirect sources would be simply ridiculous in the face of Scanderbeg's own self-presentation through his direct and renowned correspondence.

Likewise, any pious fanatic who tries to desecrate Scanderbeg's religious tolerance appears equally ridiculous in the light of his full official name: **George Castrioti Scanderbeg** - a clear symbiosis of his Epirotic soul (middle name Castrioti) between two bodies: George and Scanderbeg - symbols of the two great denominations of the world: Christianity and Islam.

Fan Noli, in his dissertation on Scanderbeg, summarized it best:

“Scanderbeg fought a long delaying action of a quarter of a century and stopped Murad II and Mehmed II long enough to make them miss the boat for Rome. As a matter of fact, Mehmed II had started his Italian campaign at Otranto in 1480, one year before he died. He was succeeded by Bayazit II, who did not bother much about conquests, and after him came Selim I, who turned his attention toward the East, thus permanently changing the center of gravity, the orientation, and the spirit of the Ottoman Empire. So Scanderbeg's delaying action, coming at a critical period,

saved Rome and Europe from the greatest catastrophe that could have befallen them. Scanderbeg's share in this highly important service can hardly be overestimated."

Scanderbeg, with his driving force as an eternal flame of freedom and nobility, absolutely represents a legendary hero; one who remained loyal to his soul and race. And in a wider, relative perspective - with his fascinating journey as a universal fighter - he represents: a "Champion of Christendom"; an ideal model of the Renaissance knight; "Iskender Bey"; and a cult of the invincible warrior.

Finally, Scanderbeg in the whole story, as Ludwig Holberg (1684–1754), philosopher and historian, recapitulated in his *Several Great Heroes...*: "was the greatest warrior, leader, and hero of Hero."

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